

HOW CAN TEACHER'S FEEDBACK IMPROVE STUDENT PERFORMANCE?

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Abstract

Feedback is an essential part of the educational process. It contrasts learners' performance to educational goals to assist them to achieve or exceed those goals. According to Scharnel (2012) effective feedback is presented in an appropriate setting, focuses on performance rather than the individual, is specific, based on direct observation or objective data, delivered using neutral, non-judgmental language, and outlines actions or plans for development. This research investigates the importance of giving feedback to students to improve their performance at Kimyo International University in Tashkent. The findings suggest that teachers play a key role in improving student performance by providing clear feedback, creating a positive and supportive learning environment, and building rapport with students. Teachers can also show students' mistakes by using non-verbal feedback, or other effective strategies, such as showing their mistakes by themselves, drilling correct answers many times, or giving them correct options and giving them a chance to correct mistakes by themselves.

Keywords: Students performance, verbal feedback, non-verbal feedback, direct and indirect feedback

Giving Feedback to Students

Introduction

“Feedback is a gift. Ideas are the currency of our next success. Let people see you value the feedback and ideas.” – (Jim Trinkia and Les Wallace) The purpose of feedback in the evaluation and development process is to enhance a student's performance rather than diminish it. The process of providing feedback must be a positive, or at least neutral, learning experience for the learner. Feedback is regarded as a difficult issue in the higher education sector. It is recognized as a crucial component for enhancing student learning. National surveys in the UK (“Higher Education Funding Council for England”, 2011) and

Australia (James, Krause, and Jennings 2010) support the above statement. There is more to being a teacher than just instructing and assisting students. It is essential to provide feedback correctly, as it has the potential to motivate students to learn more or leave them feeling frustrated. Several researchers have exchanged thoughts on this subject, but they all come to the same conclusion—that prospective teachers need to be prepared to evaluate their students' performance and offer constructive feedback. How do they provide students with useful feedback? What is the purpose of feedback for students? Others may not realize how much deeper it is. It is a means of inspiring students to work hard, develop their abilities, become self-reliant learners, and have confidence. Giving them constructive feedback can significantly improve their learning and performance.

Methodology

This research delves into "How can teacher feedback improve student performance", to comprehensively explore this topic, incorporating classroom observations with ten yes-no, questions of English Education faculty, English language classes at Kimyo International University in Tashkent. This section outlines the methodology adopted for this study. This observation allows for an understanding of the role of teachers in improving students' performance by giving feedback in foreign language classrooms. Additionally, observation of classes shows how important it is to give feedback to students to show their mistakes and achievements. For the observational component, first-year students were selected from the English Education faculty. The purposive sampling technique was employed to ensure diversity in class profiles, teaching methods, and student performance. These observations were conducted in classrooms with an average student enrollment of about 16-20. Each observation session spanned the entire class period, during which detailed field notes were taken. The observations were primarily focused on identifying how teachers give feedback and assessing the overall student's performance. Two observations were conducted at Kimyo International University in Tashkent to see how teachers give feedback and teacher-student performance. The first observation took place on 13.02.2024 during an Ancient Literature lesson. Moving forward to the second observation, conducted on 14.02.2024 during a Listening and Speaking class. A first-year class of 17 students with one female student was chosen, and the teacher's approach fostered a balanced and friendly atmosphere. This observation helps analyze how essential it is to give feedback

to students to improve their performance. Hence, feedback should be given politely and respectfully.

Findings

During the observation classes, teachers were very polite and respectful to students. After finishing the task, students started to answer questions, and the teacher corrected them by repeating the correct answer many times. After that, it was evident from the students' emotions and reactions that they understood their mistake. The most beneficial side of the teacher's technique of giving feedback was that they listened to each student till the end and, after that, corrected them by providing an additional correct answer by giving them a chance to choose the correct answer. Moreover, according to research by Wu (1971) from the University of Minnesota, students who received quick responses were able to understand the content they had just read deeper."It may not always be possible to provide students feedback right away, but sooner is better than later," the researchers stated.

Another essential part of the lesson was that the teacher supported each answer, even if it was incorrect, using more supportive words such as "maybe, interesting, very good" by Guthrie (1971), who focused primarily on response feedback rather than right/wrong feedback, did not discover any additional benefits from providing feedback after correct replies. If the feedback was given incorrectly or correctly, the outcomes might have been different. This way of responding to them kept a positive atmosphere in the classroom, and students felt supported. Every time a teacher, without any judgement, shows students mistakes in himself, he increases their knowledge and shows them how next time students can escape their mistakes and work on themselves. The positive side of the observation was that students accepted all comments without any disagreements and were ready to get more positive recommendations about their performances.

Discussion

It is simple to identify certain similarities and differences between the data in various articles and my observations and findings. There was no nonverbal feedback given during the lesson observation, however studies indicate it is just as beneficial as direct comments. Moreover, Argyle et al, (1971) showed that non-verbal cues were six times more significant than verbal cues in a related study. These percentages demonstrate that non-verbal behavior is an important form of communication for both humans and other primates, even though they may vary depending on subjective and contextual

factors and it is impossible to say which type of cue is always more important than another. When considered broadly, it refers to a technique of communication that can take many different forms, including humor, touch language, gestures, facial expressions, and gaze. (Gupta et al., 2009). According to DePaulo and Friedman (1998), nonverbal communication is a dynamic process that is crucial especially when emotions, identities, and status roles are relevant. It is also crucial when verbal communications are unclear, unreliable, or challenging to understand.

Furthermore, feedback was given throughout the observation based on the learning styles of the students. However, individuals may differ in their approaches to learning, frequently selecting different methods depending on personal preferences (Winne et al., 2003). This is an indisputable aspect of learning. One way that learners may differ is in their learning styles. These have been described as an individual's preferences and traits in the processes of absorbing, recalling, and analyzing information (Felder 1988). In a similar vein, Dantas et al., (2020) described learning styles as the favored methods by which students acquire and process information.

Recommendations

Overall, the observation demonstrates that teachers use a variety of methods to provide feedback to each student during class to assist them in comprehending their errors and achievements. Many questions were answered affirmatively, demonstrating how successfully teachers deal with feedback. It demonstrates that the teacher was able to create a welcoming environment in the classroom while additionally offering accurate feedback to the students. However, it would be better to advocate providing personalized feedback to each student after class based on their learning styles. This strategy not only assists students in understanding their mistakes but also teaches them how to deal with and prevent future problems. Additionally, teachers can use gestures, facial expressions, or other methods while providing feedback. In that way, students can feel supported and accept feedback much better. In particular cases, students can misunderstand feedback and get the impression that the teacher is judging them because comments were given during the lesson, or they may forget what the teacher said to them until the end of class. Furthermore, it is essential to establish personalized ways for students with special needs to provide feedback. Teachers can talk to students after the lesson and ask how they can help to avoid their mistakes and politely give some advice.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this research illuminates the important role of teachers in giving feedback to students to improve student's performance in university foreign language classrooms. Teachers, as highlighted through classroom observation responses, employ diverse strategies such as clear establishment of classroom norms to effectively manage disruptions. The emphasis on teachers can give feedback in different ways and use a variety of strategies such as direct, indirect, and non-verbal feedback, and feedback from the teachers play an essential role in improving students' performance. When teachers fail to comprehend how to respond appropriately, students can become depressed or even lose interest in what they are studying. This is why teachers must avoid boredom while providing feedback to students. Furthermore, teachers should provide comments politely and respectfully, without offending or judging students based on their personality or knowledge. Hence, these observations additionally proved how essential it is for students to get feedback from their teachers regarding their accomplishments and areas for improvement.

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